

Feelings of Artistic Expressions and Admittances

Literature

Keywords: person, conception, form, subject, tradition, belief, psychological process.

Jurayeva Manzura Axronkulovna

Teacher of Fergana State University. City Fergana, Uzbekistan.

Abstract

The role of a person was described in a new conceptual point of view. In this subject the modern Uzbek literature is not at the side its centre. In this point of view the reflection. The childless in the Uzbek literature was the main question, this is the way of living people, the outlook. To this was the accident. As above was said MullaAshur was even the sacred fully concretized with real life, he helped the ill people, it is a real life of the people. This it raises the interest of the pupils concerning the main plot of the story. These difficulties are shown in his sorrows, in his feeling of dissatisfaction of his life, he paid much attention to it. It influences to his psychological changes. First of all, the energetic man became at final with much shortages, with the help of unusual ways to overcome difficulties made him non-fully concerns man, discussing the problems of women and so on.

The role of a person was described in a new conceptual point of view. Though: “the reason of a life appearance and it’s death reasons, besides the person’s life reasons and their ends, even the reasons of a person’s life were surrounded wet mystery” [1, p. 46]. You understand this mystery, to recognize the being, depend on itself, its certain importance and magnificence.

In this subject the modern Uzbek literature is not at the side it’s centre. In this point of view the reflection. In of this new person’s conception is differ from former century ZulfiyaKuralbay daughter’s story: “The call of death” it’s plot and composition of a little, not.... at the same time it shows a little unusual form of a new person’s view can be the certain example to it, at the Beginning of the novel at MullaAshur’s example we can see not an usual man’s appearance, but another man’s appearance, it’s development: “MullaAshur was the village’s sincere prayer, he had many admires, had impressive treatment and there were ruinous about him. Once, one the rich man’s face became wrong and in one night by praying the prayer made him right and well, he preyed three time for it.

In the village Tokay the old man Satto was bitten by scorpion, he was saved by this worship. A five-year old grandson of HosilMirob either from fear or from other reason he couldn’t say a word, it was worship Ashur, who helped the boy. [2, p. 65]. By the given examples we can see that MullaAshur was a very capable man, he had sincere ability. From one point of view it was a legend of the West. According to the mistery heroes, at that time the wishers of people were depended on people. But the word “it were” we begin with these words and “the rumours” these words, when we use them we cannot believe that it was true. Even in the story by the teller’s words: “what are there true and what are there false it is very difficult to recognize. Though it is true the given examples maybe shown to the worship the people had been recovered. Here MullaAshur is told to be unsincere and pompous descriptions about him appeared problems. Till these accidents MullaAshur became the sacred man, became prominent image of traditions now

he appeared with another image of speciality: He himself without lack of something he helped everybody, but himself, he lived without helping to himself. He hadn't children [2, p. 65]. He was childless, The childless in the Uzbek literature was the main question, this is the way of living people, the outlook. To this was the accident. As above was said MullaAshur was even the sacred fully concretized with real life, he helped the ill people, it is a real life of the people.

This it raises the interest of the pupils concerning the main plot of the story. These difficulties are shown in his sorrows, in his feeling of unsatisfaction of his life, he paid much attention to it. It influences to his psychological changes. First of all, the energetic man became at final with much shortages, with the help of unusual ways to overcome difficulties made him non-fully concerns man, discussing the problems of women and so on.

At the developing of this force of the plot the accidents are developing, they were paid attention at the further main movements were shown. Besides it mulla He himself full-blooded person, other, men like persons, or being he began to invite them in order to prove it. In his opinion his former wife had taken away her things, he wanted to show it How brave man he was, He wanted to be acquainted with a woman. After this part the teller takes the natural way. t.e such kind of a man couldn't be without his family and the pupils thought about MullaAshur's wife the artistic information is given: "His woman Honimbuvi a poor bone she is a tender woman, they are married for already 8 years, though she couldn't look at her husband's eyes, She is embarrassing, incapable to the words, and shy. [2, p. 65-66] It is shown that Hanimbuvi's image is almost on the contrary, her husband is very strict, he is perfect at words, he is in good relations with any people, and Hanimbuvi is not good for words She is shy, embarrassing, Such description of a woman, first of all, MullaAshur depicted as a man with loneless with loss heart, and it concern his accident with his fate, Because the worship with strong prays and without his son it depended on his heredity. Though MullaAshur's first wife's life courcerned to his second marriage Because firstly formerly

MullaAshur's first marriage to man's Hoji's little daughter, he had lived with her for 15 years. And in the right way he was divorced, Buvrajob married another man and she had children then, MullaAshur is still childless and he is still alone. And with these thoughts and willings he lived and he wanted to marry a beautiful woman. Hu aim of his thoughts a similar as his death His age about 70 years, with his first wife, and then 8 years, with the second wife and we can consider that he was nearly 50 years. His outlook, his thoughts and feelings, every man can live as the God wishes, there is an old saying says at that time such kind of sayings can't be believing and it can't be artistic story. At the new period the writer describes his hero in another image. We should say in that way that above mentioned story and the developing idea, problems, the themes of 70-80-ies can be met in those stories too. But there is a great difference between them in their images and in artistic-asthetic piece. His former ideological demands there should be historical-artistic historical-biographical. Demands require the real images concerning MullaAshur's form he is depicted in a new way of image, at this place it is shown a new way of person's conception. It is depicted in a new society views and mixed form. This is first of all, each having a shortage of tendency,

everything is in one balance in heaven rule and in the second place the person who dreamed all his life to the happiness and joyfulness and to see his life ideal to the death, Everybody afraid of death angel, and indeed the Angel of death and the beauty angel as an example was shown, Her appearance, of the woman's angel is the following description:".

“Among the two days once a young woman appeared before Mulla I want you to do me an amulet Mulla was sitting on the many quilts and was shocked at these words. He didn't look at all at the woman who came to him with proposals and this time he looked at her with interest, her voice was very tender. They together were very tired very full of sorrows, they were alone together, Mulla was shivering when this woman appeared. He didn't feel how she had gone away.”[2, p. 66]MullaAshur tried to relax, to come to himself but he couldn't concentrate. Though he was twice married he firstly felt himself in such away he was at a loss at first in his life. He was, married two times, but he was in a difficulty. In the evening he came into his room, closed the door and there was a little carpet in which he prayed. Then he sat on the little carpet and began to pray. He was praying 3 days, and at last he went out of the room. He became thin and pale. Here we can see How MullaAshur's behavior and the changes in him were enough to be seen in this story.

The writer in this story was describing here, Mulla's belief, two forces-Angel and Devil, they fight between them. Here is depicted the fights between the West and Europe literature the lasting fight maybe shown in the story But the aim of the story here is somehow in another way.

“MullaAshur saw twice that woman in the early morning, He noticed as if somebody was watching him, he takes me at one hand a jug and after washing he showed his steps, he turned around. Gazing around, looking here and there not far from there, standing near the metal gates he noticed there that woman, he again was shivering Here he again was shocked and he was watching her view[2, p. 73].But Honimbuvi didn't see him. Mulla became at a loss at this situation. For the first time he became joy. This way in the face of a woman near the country house, on the way of the road, or near the home, he was met by her, But now he as before as if he was a traitor, and now in order to be cleaned himself he didn't pray, he was not shy, he didn't turn his face, he didn't get away from his thoughts, and the reflections. Now he didn't pray, five-times a day, he didn't help people who need his help, and didn't take a sacred book into his hands now he felt himself as a bird and he was very easy. Here he changed greatly and he was full of energy and the woman was a great help to him, we can see it in the image of a woman, the upper thoughts and believes he thought about other things. Here MullaAshur in the example of reaching a beautiful woman we can see how other things became important for him. Here we see a new conception was opened. Childless and the will to live happily, loneliness was the problem, he was not satisfied of himself the world outlook and his spirit became and made a dream. In his dream he was walking with her somewhere holding her hand. Sometimes dark, sometimes bright, they passed dangerous places, as a snake's footprint and the broken houses and with broken frames, the damaged houses, as if some people were looking at them, Green grass there they sat and she sat

there, it seemed they were happy. they were laughing at them, His heart was trembling, from the feelings Mulla looked at he kneeled before, at that time he stroked her face, She melted and put her head on him. At that time the inner heart of Mulla was with sorrow, he didn't feel himself better than others and the religious education was higher than shame. Each person here the essence of tendency is the person's activity began to change. This is together with death, it is shown at the end of the story.

One more side should be paid attention. This Mulla Ashur's thoughts with Honimbuvi disappear, they refused. Honimbuvi began to worry about her husband. The woman began to worry about this thoughts, thinking's, and spirits as they all were in her thoughts.... Honimbuvi worried about the changes in her husband. She felt that something or somebody impressed on him, His thoughts they try to return his eating, house-hold things. But their hopelessness is moving farther from their life; they are rude to each other it was her fault to be in such a situation.

In the conclusion we should say that the Modern Uzbek stories are, the mental position of their dissatisfaction of life, there are many other general taska in the person's psychological beliefs, behavior and politeness, they are shown in a new appearance, it's shown here in this story. From one point of view it is a tragedy it is the accident is similar to the life but there is the importance of a person. And greatness, we can follow it with these specific features Mulla Ashur became mysterious and majestic hero.

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